

PASSIVE EUTHANASIA: A RIGHT CHOICE?

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ABSTRACT

The word "euthanasia" is derived from the Greek words "Eu" and "Thanatos," which means "Good Death." Passive euthanasia can be termed as intentionally letting a patient die by withholding artificial life support such as a ventilator or feeding tube. Terminally ill patients are accelerated through passive euthanasia to relieve them of pain and suffering. In the 17th century, Francis Bacon referred to a happy and painless death, as doctors must alleviate the suffering of patients. The House of Lords selected a committee on Medical Ethics in England. The European Association of Palliative Care (EPAC) Ethics task force, in a discussion in 2003, said that "the killing of a patient without the consent of the patient is not euthanasia". Hence, consent is required in passive euthanasia, i.e., it should be voluntary only. The issue of passive euthanasia was triggered by the case of P. Rathinam VS Union of India (1994), where the Supreme Court interpreted the right to life under article 21 as inclusive of the right to die. The case of Gina Kaur VS State of Punjab (1996) identifies the right to refuse medical assistance. The Court refuses to expressly determine the validity and legality of euthanasia.

On March 9, 2018, the Supreme Court of India legalized passive euthanasia utilizing the withdrawal of life support to patients in permanent vegetative states [PVS]. The Historic Judgment was passed on the Aruna Shanbaug Case, which was a landmark case on passive euthanasia in India.

In this article, because passive euthanasia is the right choice, different arguments are placed in favor of the topic. Historically, passive euthanasia tends to focus on many concerns. Many questions arise: Does passive euthanasia violate a patient's right to die? Is seeing our loved one suffering from pain ethical? What is better for a terminally ill person suffering from pain or a peaceful death? This article throws a huge light on the importance of passive euthanasia in India.

INTRODUCTION

Mankind has always struggled to deal with different kinds of illnesses that have existed for so long. Sometimes there are situations where living becomes more problematic and the victim or a close one contemplates the end of the patient's life. The practice of ending the life of a patient to relieve him/her from the pain and suffering is called "euthanasia." **Passive Euthanasia** is the ending of one person's life by another in the best interest of the person who dies, through artificial life support such as a ventilator or feeding tube. **Euthanasia** can also be termed as **Mercy Killing** or **Assisted Suicide**, as it is undertaken with the aid of another person. It is also known as "physician-assisted suicide" (PAS). Passive euthanasia is performed on patients who are experiencing severe pain due to terminal illness, as death seems to be much better than suffering.

In modern society, there are so many controversies around passive euthanasia. Passive euthanasia can save the patient from suffering a poor quality of life, as terminal illness can make life vulnerable and painful. At this point, the life of the patient becomes weak, they lose their dignity, and life becomes pointless. Every person has the right to choose how they want to live and die. They have a full right to avoid a painful life and can opt for death instead. Terminally ill diseases are not all cost-efficient as they have expensive medical treatments and medication. Also, understaffed medical facilities are provided as patients' chances of surviving are lower. The right to refuse medical treatment gives way to passive euthanasia as a patient who is terminally ill can't be cured through severe medications. For example, organ failure, Alzheimer's disease, brain tumors, blindness, and deafness. It is expensive to keep a person alive when there is no clear cause for their illness. Such patients lose their morale and thus think of giving up. Passive Euthanasia would release precious resources to treat people who could live. It encourages patients to consider organ donation. Euthanasia not only gives the "right to die" but also the "right to life" of patients who require organs and thus can save many lives. Seeing our loved ones

suffering from such pain and trauma, even when the proper medications are administered, is tough for family members. The psychological pain for both patients and their families is horrifying.

According to a survey carried out by 200 doctors by the society of Right to Die with Dignity in Bombay, 95% of doctors said they had the topic in mind and were concerned. 78% believed that patients have the right to choose in cases of terminal illness, 74% believed that artificial life support should be extended, 65% would withdraw life support systems, and 41% argued that life should be respected, and 31% had some reservations about the concerned issues. The landmark case in passive euthanasia was the Aruna Shanbaugh case.

1) Aruna Shambaugh (born June 1, 1948; died May 5, 2015):

Aruna Shambaugh was a nurse at King Edward Memorial Hospital, Mumbai. In 1973, she was assaulted by a ward boy while she was changing clothes in the hospital basement by Valmiki. He strangled her neck with a dog chain, which made her blind, deaf, and paralyzed as the oxygen supply was cut off. She suffered in a vegetative state for the next 42 years. On May 18, 2015, she died due to severe pneumonia. She was on ventilator support.

The Supreme Court's decision:

On March 9, 2018, the Supreme Court of India legalized passive euthanasia using withdrawing life support from patients in a permanent vegetative state (PVS). The decision was made by the Aruna Shanbaugh case as she was in PVS until she died in 2015. This landmark decision established guidelines for the legalization of passive euthanasia in India. The guidelines were that the decision to withdraw treatment or discontinue life support must be taken by parents, spouse, or close relatives, or in the absence of them, by a close friend. The changes to passive euthanasia were triggered by the Aruna Shanbaugh case.

2) Anamika Misra:

A Kanpur woman wrote to the Prime Minister requesting passive euthanasia for her daughter, Anamika Misra, who had muscular dystrophy disease. Her father, Shashi Misra, who was 59, died due to the same disease. It is a genetic disorder that leads to the increase, weakening, and breakdown of skeletal muscle. She said the letter she wrote to the PM seeking help for financial assistance was assisted by 50,000 Rs.

3) Uttar Pradesh's Jeet Narayan:

Jeet Narayan, who was from Mirzapur, UP, In 2008, he pleaded for passive euthanasia for his four sons, Durgesh (22), Sarvesh (18), Brijesh (13), and Sushil (10). As all were crippled and paralyzed below the neck. He wrote to the President of India, but his plea was later rejected.

4) Dennis Kumar, Kanyakumari:

Dennis Kumar from the Kanyakumari district asked the district collector to grant passive euthanasia for his infant son who was suffering from an unknown disease. As he was unable to bear the expenses of treatment, he asked to have passive euthanasia. However, the court rejected the plea in 2008.

WORLDWIDE PASSIVE EUTHANASIA SCENARIO

Passive euthanasia is currently legal in seven jurisdictions.

- 1. The Netherlands:** On April 1, 2001, passive euthanasia became legal. The ministry of public health and support for well-being allows a person to end their life with dignity after having received every available type of palliative care.
- 2. Belgium:** On May 28th, 2012, passive euthanasia will be legalized. Belgium is one of the five countries that allow doctors to kill patients as

per their will, and one of the two, along with the Netherlands, grants the procedure to people with mental illness.

- 3. Luxembourg:** The Passive Euthanasia Bill was passed by the Chamber of Deputies on March 19th, 2009. **On December 15th, 2014,** the constitutional court of Colombia legalized passive euthanasia.
- 4. Canada: Passive Euthanasia** was legalized by the Parliament of Canada on June 17, 2016. This bill received considerable multiparty opposition from the senate, but after that, they made different amendments that were accepted by the House of Commons, except one.
- 5. Victoria and Western Australia:** Victoria was the first one to accept Passive Euthanasia in June 2019, and Western Australia passed the same on December 2.
- 6. Spain:** On June 25th, 2021, passive euthanasia was legalized by the Cortes Generales. On the 18th of March 2021, Spain's parliament voted in favor of the final reading, thus making it law. It was sanctioned by the king on the 24th of March 2021. The law came into force on the 25th of June 2021, exactly 3 months after.

THE CONCLUSION

To conclude, passive euthanasia doesn't mean taking the life of the patient. The doctor should do everything humanly possible to save the patient's life. However, some suffering is not reversible, and to reduce the pain, death becomes the last option. India has initiated a national debate and working law to safeguard it and prevent misuse of it.

The court has said that the right to live does not include the right to die by implication, but there can always be a separate right to die. The landmark Supreme Court judgment has provided a major boost to passive euthanasia. Therefore, passive euthanasia is always the right choice. As such, it is better to die rather than to live in traumatic and painful conditions.

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